

A DISCRETE MESOSCOPIC FINITE ELEMENT MODEL USED TO LINK THE MANUFACTURING PROCESS TO THE FINAL PART STIFFNESS

Cynthia Mitchell¹ and James Sherwood¹

¹Department of Mechanical Engineering, University of Massachusetts Lowell
1 University Ave., Lowell, MA, 01851, USA

Email: james_sherwood@uml.edu, web page: <http://www.uml.edu/acmtrl>

Keywords: Characterization, Finite Element Analysis, Manufacturing, Textile Composite

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a methodology for extending the use of the beam-shell forming model to predict the structural properties of a textile-reinforced composite components and structures. The aforementioned finite element model uses a discrete mesoscopic approach to simulate the forming of structures and has the ability to predict the severity and location of potential manufacturing defects. Beam elements are used to represent the fiber yarns or tows, while shell elements are used to represent the shear stiffness of the textile. After the forming simulation has been performed, the material definition will be changed such that the beam elements will represent the fiber reinforcements and the shell elements will represent the matrix material. The methodology behind the entire approach will be demonstrated using a stitched uniaxial glass fabric. The established experiments used to characterize the dry fabric behavior will be discussed and demonstrated. The methodology that has been developed to characterizing the cured composite behavior by discretizing the contribution of the matrix and reinforcement to the overall composite stiffness will be introduced. To demonstrate the capabilities of this new model, a plate reinforced with sheared fabric will be tested. The results of a forming model using the same geometry will be used to create a model of the same part. The finite element model will be compared with experimental data to validate the proposed methodology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Composite materials have become increasingly popular in many industries for their potential to produce lightweight structures while achieving high stiffness and high strength [1-3]. For example, the automotive and aerospace industries are adopting composites to create fuel-efficient lightweight vehicles [4]. Similarly, the wind energy industry takes advantage of composite structures to build long, lightweight turbine blades, which in turn maximize the potential power output of the turbine [5].

Specifically, fiber-reinforced composites are known for their superior mechanical properties and lightweight structure. Material in fiber format is a common reinforcement because it generally performs better than the same material in bulk format. The probability of defects is much smaller in fibers due to their smaller volume, which statistically results in a higher strength. Fibers also offer flexibility in molding complex shapes. A smaller diameter allows forming of curvatures with smaller induced strains and therefore a lower potential for breaking. Long-fibers are maximize the load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement, making them a popular reinforcement format[1].

Textile-reinforced composites are a subset of fiber-reinforced composites in which the bundles of fibers (a.k.a. tows) have been woven or stitched together prior to being used as a reinforcing material. Textiles are attractive because they are relatively inexpensive and they save time in composite processing by allowing the manufacturer to lay-up multiple plies and orientations at once. Many forming methods have also been developed to decrease the production time of textile-reinforced composite structures through rapid, automated manufacturing processes (e.g., matched die forming, thermoforming, and hydroforming) that allow for relatively quick molding of two-dimensional sheets into three-dimensional parts [6].

During the forming of complex curvatures, there are two major modes of deformation occurring within the textile: the tows can stretch and the fabric can shear. As the reinforcement material is

typically made from stiff fibers, in-plane shear becomes the primary mode of deformation [7]. An example of this shearing mechanism is shown Fig. 1, which depicts the deformation of a woven fabric during the forming of a hemisphere. The tows that were originally perpendicular rotate with respect to each other to conform to the three-dimensional geometry.

Fig. 1: Shear deformation of a woven fabric formed into a hemisphere.

There are two popular methods to measure a fabric's resistance to in-plane shear: the bias extension test and the picture frame test (a.k.a. trellis frame test, shear frame test, rhombus test). A bias extension test (Fig. 2(a)) deforms the fabric by a uniaxial load on the fabric in the 45° directions [8, 9]. This particular loading condition creates a central region of pure shear and four surrounding regions with half of the shear deformation experienced by the central region (Fig. 2(b)).

Fig. 2: Bias extension (a) test setup and (b) deformation zones

The picture frame test is performed by clamping a sample of fabric to a rigid frame. A load is applied in the bias direction of the frame, causing the frame and fabric to deform in a state of pure shear [7, 10-12]. An example of a picture frame test is shown in Fig. 3(a). The test area is in the center of the fabric sample. The "arms" of the sample are clamped into the frame, and the cross-fibers in the arms are removed to ensure a state of pure shear in the test area [7]. The typical load vs. shear angle curve is shown in Fig. 3(b). When the fabric begins to shear, the loads required to rotate the tows are relatively low. As the fabric continues to shear, it reaches a point where further rotation is hindered by the compaction of the tows against one another, thereby increasing the shear stiffness of the fabric. Once the tows can no longer compact, the fabric is said to have reached its "locking angle." At this point, the load required to further shear the fabric increases significantly, and the fabric tows begin to buckle out of the plane of the fabric [10]. Studies have been performed to predict the locking angle based on fabric architecture using a pin-joint model [12, 13] as well as using the microstructure of the fabric tow [14].

Fig. 3: Picture frame (a) test setup and (b) typical load vs. shear angle response [10].

Researchers have also done extensive work to examine how in-plane shear loading deforms the textile on the microscopic and mesoscopic level. Many publications have demonstrated that the shape of the fiber tow changes as in-plane shear is introduced to the textile [15-18]. Additionally, researchers have observed an increase in thickness with respect to increasing shear angle [19, 20]. While extensive studies have been performed to understand the shear deformation mechanics of fabrics during forming processes, very little research exists examining how shearing of the fabric affects the composite structure. This paper will examine how in-plane shear within the fabric reinforcements affects the flexural behavior of a woven-glass reinforced composite plate.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEEDURES

To investigate the effect of in-plane shear of the fabric reinforcement on the resulting flexural properties of a flat composite plate, samples were fabricated with a prescribed uniform shear angle in the fabric. This section describes the techniques used to fabricate the samples and the tests performed to evaluate the bending stiffnesses of the plates.

2.1. Sample Fabrication

The samples were manufactured from a plain-weave Twintex® fabric consisting of comingled fiberglass (reinforcement) and polypropylene (matrix) fibers. To ensure that each sample was uniformly sheared to the desired angle, the fabric was placed in a picture frame (Fig. 4(a)). The frame that was used had an edge length of 254 mm while the edge of the test area had an edge length of 219 mm. The cross-tows were removed from the “arms” of the sample to ensure a uniform state of shear in the central region. The frame was displaced until the fabric reached the desired shear angle. The bolts on the frame were then tightened such that the fabric would not relax (Fig. 4(b)). The fabric was subsequently lined with non-porous teflon paper and rubber to reduce bleed-out of the matrix material and to create a smooth plate surface (Fig. 4(c)). To ensure that the fabric would remain flat inside the vacuum bag, an aluminum plate was machined to the deformed dimensions of the test area (Fig. 4(d)). Once the layup was completed, the entire setup was placed in a vacuum bag and placed in the oven (Fig. 4(e)).

Fig. 4: Layup process for sheared-fabric-reinforced plates.

Per the manufacturer's specifications [21], the temperature of the sample was monitored until it reached a steady state at 180°C. At this temperature, the polypropylene fibers had melted to form the molten matrix which was allowed to flow throughout the sample due to the vacuum conditions. The oven was turned off, and the sample cooled to room temperature under vacuum to consolidate the liquid polypropylene. After the matrix was completely consolidated, the sample was removed from the vacuum bag.

The consolidated samples were then cut into 127-mm \times 127-mm square plates. The plates were cut such that the weft tows were parallel to one edge of the plate which will be referred to as the global x -axis. The warp tows were rotated from the other edge, referred to as the global y -axis of the plate by the shear angle (γ). This configuration can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5: Schematic of sheared-fabric-reinforced plates.

Plates were manufactured for shear angles of 0°, 10°, 20°, 25°, and 30°. For each angle, three samples were manufactured to explore repeatability of the test results. The thickness of each plate was measured at 16 discrete locations around the perimeter of the plate. The measurements were averaged and the relationship between degree of shear and plate thickness is shown in Fig. 6(a). Similar to literature findings for dry fabrics [19, 20], the thickness of the plate increased with an increasing shear angle. To ensure that the fiber volume fraction of each plate did not change significantly with respect to shear angle, the mass of each plate was measured and the density of each plate was calculated. It can be seen in Fig. 6(b) that the mass also increases with increasing shear angle. Fig. 6(c) shows that the densities of the plates are independent of the shear angle in the fabric reinforcement, indicating that the assumption of a constant volume fraction over all the samples is valid.

Fig. 6: Variation of (a) thickness, (b) mass, and (c) density with respect to reinforcement shear angle.

2.2. Bend Tests

Bend tests were performed on the samples to investigate how the degree of shear within the textile reinforcement effected the flexural stiffness of the plate. Each plate was tested on an Instron 4464 universal testing machine with a 100-N load cell using a three-point bend test setup as is shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7. Bend test experimental setup.

The supports were spaced 98-mm apart and a uniform deflection was applied across the middle of the plate. The tests were closely monitored to ensure that the deflection occurred within the linear-elastic range of the material. No failure was observed during the tests.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Each plate was tested four times. First, the plate was bent about the global y -axis such that the weft tows were experiencing a bending load in the x -direction. The plate was then subsequently rotated 90° and bend about the global x -axis such that it was loaded in the y -direction. To ensure the plates were symmetric, the plate was then flipped over to apply a negative curvature to the weft and perpendicular directions respectively. The results were then averaged for each test and the results are reported in Fig. 8. The error bars denote the standard deviation. To avoid damaging the samples, small deflections were applied to the plate to ensure purely elastic deformation. Therefore the slope of each load-displacement curve is directly proportional to the effective stiffness of the sample.

Fig. 8. Bend test results for (a) x -direction and (b) y -direction.

The slopes of the average load-displacement data are listed in Table 1. Fig. 8(a) and Table 1 show that the stiffness of the plate in the x -direction (i.e. aligned with the weft tows) increased as the fabric shear angle increased. However, the results of the tests loaded in the y -direction as shown in Fig. 8(b) were unexpected. Instead of the stiffness decreasing as the fibers were sheared away from the warp direction, a slight decrease was noticed in the 10° and 20° sheared plates but an increase in stiffness was observed in the 25° and 30° sheared plates. To understand this phenomenon, Classical Laminate Theory (CLT) was used to understand the mechanics of an anisotropic plate in flexure.

Shear Angle [°]	X-Direction		Y-Direction	
	Avg. Slope [N/mm]	Std. Dev.	Avg. Slope [N/mm]	Std. Dev.
0	0.558	0.037	0.714	0.035
10	0.585	0.038	0.693	0.110
20	0.638	0.036	0.692	0.031
25	0.739	0.045	0.715	0.027
30	0.880	0.076	0.810	0.031

Table 1. Slopes of average load-displacement curves for plates with varying fabric shear angles.

CLT is used to relate applied loads on a laminate to the stresses, strains, and deflections of the composite structure [2]. The laminate stiffness matrix, commonly referred to as the ABD matrix, relates the strains in the composite to the applied loads through the following relations:

$$\begin{pmatrix} N_x \\ N_y \\ N_{xy} \\ M_x \\ M_y \\ M_{xy} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} A_{11} & A_{12} & A_{16} & B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} \\ A_{12} & A_{22} & A_{26} & B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} \\ A_{16} & A_{26} & A_{66} & B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} \\ B_{11} & B_{12} & B_{16} & D_{11} & D_{12} & D_{16} \\ B_{12} & B_{22} & B_{26} & D_{12} & D_{22} & D_{26} \\ B_{16} & B_{26} & B_{66} & D_{16} & D_{26} & D_{66} \end{bmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \varepsilon^o_x \\ \varepsilon^o_y \\ \gamma^o_{xy} \\ \kappa^o_x \\ \kappa^o_y \\ \kappa^o_{xy} \end{pmatrix}. \quad (1)$$

All of the laminates tested were symmetric. Therefore, by definition, $B_{ij} = 0$. The bend tests performed enforced a curvature about one axis of the plates, i.e. $\kappa^o_x \neq 0$ and $\varepsilon^o_x = \varepsilon^o_y = \gamma^o_{xy} = \kappa^o_y = \kappa^o_{xy} = 0$. Therefore, the resultant forces can be simplified from Eqn. 3 to:

$$M_x = D_{11}\kappa^o_x \quad (2.1)$$

$$M_y = D_{12}\kappa^o_x \quad (2.2)$$

$$M_{xy} = D_{16}\kappa^o_x \quad (2.3)$$

The plates with 0° shear angles are cross-ply laminates, so by definition, $D_{16} = 0$. These plates will experience a bending moment, M_x , and a moment resulting from the Poisson effect, M_y . However, the plates with nonzero shear will also experience a twisting moment, M_{xy} , from the bend-twist coupling present in composites. Two factors were considered that could possibly affect the stiffness values D_{11} , D_{12} , and D_{16} —the cross section of the fiber tow and the thickness of the laminate.

3.1. Effect of Tow Cross-Section on Bending Stiffness

One factor that can influence bending stiffness is the cross-sectional shape of the fiber tows. The tows of the textile considered in this research are made of glass fibers, which provide most of the stiffness to the composite. Due to their long, slender geometry, these fiber tows can be considered as beams. The cross-sectional shape not only affects the area moment of inertia of the beam, I , but also the torsional constant, J . Since the plates with shear present within the fabric reinforcement will experience bend-twist coupling, understanding the areal distribution of the fiber tows is important to understanding their behavior.

An edge of each tested plate was cut off and polished. Images of the cross-sections were taken on a Zeiss V20 Stereo Microscope. A representative set of cross-sections of the plates with 0° shear angles within the fabric reinforcement is given in Fig. 9. The cross-sectional shapes of the fiber tows are consistent throughout the plate.

Fig. 9: Cross-section of the weft tows with 0° shear angle in fabric reinforcement.

The cross-sections of the plates with a 25° shear angle are shown in Fig. 10. Unlike the plates with no shear deformation in the reinforcement, the cross-section is not consistent. Tows appear to rotate at different locations throughout the plate. This behavior has the potential to have a direct effect on the bending and torsional stiffness of the “beam” reinforcement.

Fig. 10: Cross-section of the weft tows with 25° shear angle in fabric reinforcement.

To investigate any possible effect of this tow deformation on the bending stiffness, a finite element model was used to model the glass and the resin discretely using a methodology introduced in [22]. This model uses a unit cell approach (Fig. 11) to represent the textile reinforced composite.

Fig. 11: Finite element approach used to discretely represent a woven-fabric-reinforced composite.

A shell element is used to represent the matrix material. Each shell edge shares a node with a beam element that represents the fiber tow. The fiber was modeled both with and without the observed twist. The model was used with material properties provided from the manufacturer instead of characterizing the composite stiffness. Since the goal of the modeling was to understand the effect of the cross-section deformation, only approximate material properties were necessary. Thus the model was not expected to follow the trends observed experimentally.

3.2. Geometric Model for Fabric Shear

To assist in developing an understanding of the geometric effects of fabric shear, a geometric model was created based on the equations presented by Barbero in [23]. To keep the model relatively simple, the midplane of each tow was considered instead of the entire cross-section. A plot of a Representative Volume Element (RVE) comprised of the midsurfaces of each tow is shown in Fig. 12.

Fig. 12: Representative volume element comprised of tow midsurfaces.

The undulation in the z -direction of the weft tows along the x -axis, z_f , can be described as:

$$z_f(x, y) = -\frac{t-h_f}{2} \cos \frac{\pi x}{w_w+g_w} \quad (3)$$

where t represents the overall thickness of the fabric, h_f represents the height of the weft tows, w_w represents the width of the warp tows, and g_w represents the gap between the warp tows. Similarly the undulations in the z -direction of the warp tows along the y -axis, z_w , can be defined as:

$$z_w(x, y) = \frac{t-h_w}{2} \cos \frac{\pi y}{w_f+g_f} \quad (4)$$

where h_w represents the height of the warp tows, w_f represents the width of the weft tows, and g_w represents the gap between the weft tows.

When the fabric is in the undeformed state, the local and global coordinate systems are the coincident. The weft yarns run parallel to the local x -axis and the warp yarns run parallel to the local y -axis as shown in Fig. 13(a). When the fabric shears the local and global coordinate systems begin to deviate. In the generic example depicted in Fig. 13(b), the local x -axis has been rotated from the global X -axis by some angle α . Likewise. The local y -axis has been rotated from the global Y -axis by some angle β .

Fig. 13: Global and local coordinate systems of (a) undeformed and (b) sheared fabric unit cells.

The transformation from the local coordinate system to the global coordinate system can be described using the following equations:

$$X = x \cos \alpha + y \sin \beta \quad (5)$$

$$Y = x \sin \alpha + y \cos \beta \quad (6)$$

When fabric is sheared in a picture frame test or a bias extension test, the deformation is considered uniform such that for a given shear angle, γ , the rotations are equal to $\alpha = \beta = \gamma/2$.

For plates considered in this paper, fabric reinforcement was sheared such that the local x -axis and global X -axis remained parallel, i.e. $\alpha = 0$ and the local y -axis was rotated from the global Y -axis by the prescribed shear angle, i.e. $\beta = \gamma$. Therefore, Equations (5) and (6) can be rewritten as:

$$X = x + y \sin \gamma \quad (7)$$

$$Y = y \cos \gamma \quad (8)$$

Equations (3) and (4) describe the undulation of the yarns in the local coordinate system. To understand how the yarns behave in the global coordinate system, they are combined with Equations (7) and (8) to produce:

$$z_f(X, Y, \gamma) = -\frac{t-h_f}{2} \cos \frac{\pi(X-Y \tan \gamma)}{w_w+g_w} \quad (9)$$

$$z_w(X, Y, \gamma) = \frac{t-h_w}{2} \cos \frac{\pi Y}{(w_f+g_f) \cos \gamma}. \quad (10)$$

The cross-section of the beam element is defined by the plane perpendicular to the midline of the fiber tow. This can be seen in Fig. 14. As the fiber tow shears within the woven fabric, there is minimal deformation to the true cross-section of the tow. However, the perpendicular cross-section implemented into the beam element changes as the tow shears. To properly model the tows using beam elements, the change in this cross-section must be understood and captured by the model. Equation 9 can be used to model the midplane of the weft tows based off the coordinates of a point and the shear angle within the fabric.

Fig. 14. Schematic of sheared tow as it will be implemented into a beam element.

Fig. 15 shows how the cross-section changes along different points of the yarn for increasing shear angles. When there is no shear (0° , top row of the chart in Fig. 15), the only change along an undulation period is the height of the cross-section. As soon as any shear angle is introduced to the fabric, the deformation of the tow causes the perpendicular cross-section to appear twisted. This twist deformation increases with increasing shear angles. This modeling result agrees what has been seen experimentally.

Fig. 15: Variation in cross-section location and orientation along the length of an undulation period as a function of shear angle.

Implementing this complex behavior into the existing beam-shell model is not possible due to the simplification of each tow having a constant cross-section along each beam element. Thus, the twist of the cross-section, ϕ , can be approximated by the equation:

$$\phi(X, \gamma) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{z_f(X, w_f/2, \gamma) - z_f(X, -w_f/2, \gamma)}{w(\gamma)} \right) \quad (11)$$

where Equation 6 is evaluated for $Y = w_f/2$ and $Y = -w_f/2$. Substituting equation 8 into equation 11 yields:

$$\phi(X, \gamma) = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{(h_f - t) \sin\left(\frac{\pi X}{w_w + g_w}\right) \sin\left(\frac{\pi w_{f_0} \sin \gamma}{2(w_w + g_w)}\right)}{w_{f_0} \cos \gamma} \right). \quad (12)$$

The twist along an undulation period is shown in Fig. 16(a). The twist demonstrates a periodic behavior over the undulation period of the tow. One undulation period corresponds to two unit cells as represented by the beam-shell model. To implement the twist of the cross-section into the beam-shell model, the twist angle was averaged over a unit cell. This is shown in Fig. 16(b).

Fig. 16: Twist angle of cross section: (a) calculated along an undulation period and (b) averaged over the unit cell.

3.3. Fiber Twist Implemented into the Beam-Shell Model

Beam/shell models were generated for plates in which the fabric reinforcement had been sheared 0° , 10° , 20° , 25° , and 30° similar to the plates tested. The plates were subjected to a 3-point bend test about the global X-axis and the global Y-axis. The load-displacement curves were calculated using the finite element method with Abaqus/Standard. Each model was then re-calculated with the estimated twist implemented into the beam cross-section definition. The slopes of the calculated load-displacement curve are reported in Fig. 17. While the slopes of the finite element models change as a function of shear within the fabric reinforcement, the twisting deformation of the fiber tow does not have a significant effect on the bending stiffness.

Fig. 17: Calculated load-displacement curves for 3-point-bend tests of beam-shell models with and without beam cross-section twist in (a) the global X-direction and (b) the global Y-direction

3.4. Effect of Thickness on Bending Stiffness

Another factor that affects the bending stiffness of the plates is the thickness of the plates. For a single-ply plate, the flexural stiffness constants, D_{11} , D_{12} , and D_{16} are defined as:

$$D_{11} = \frac{1}{4} \bar{Q}_{11} t^3 \quad (13.1)$$

$$D_{12} = \frac{1}{4} \bar{Q}_{12} t^3 \quad (13.2)$$

$$D_{16} = \frac{1}{4} \bar{Q}_{16} t^3 \quad (13.3)$$

Therefore, each of the moments applied to the plate, M_x , M_y , and M_{xy} , to enforce a curvature about a single axis are directly proportional to the cube of the plate thickness. The reinforcement shear angle correlated with a change in plate thickness (Fig. 6). To effectively remove this dependence from the data, the average measured slopes reported in Table 1 were divided by cube of the measured plate thicknesses depicted in Fig. 6(a). The normalized load-displacement slopes are shown for the X-direction in Fig. 18(a) and for the Y-direction in Fig. 18(b). The trends observed are more consistent with the expected trends based solely on reorientation of the fibers within the plate. As the shear angle increases, the normalized slope in the weft direction increases and the normalized slope in the perpendicular direction decreases.

Fig. 18: Slope of load-displacement curves normalized by cubed thickness for (a) x-direction and (b) y-direction.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of shear deformation on the flexural stiffness of a fabric-reinforced composite plate was studied in this paper. Plates with a pre-determined shear angle in the fabric reinforcement were manufactured and tested in flexure. The change in bending stiffness of the plates displayed trends that were not solely consistent with reorientation of the fibers. Changes in the shape and in the orientation of the cross-sections of the tows were observed for plates with shear present in the fabric reinforcement. These changes are attributed to the local shear deformation of the fiber tow. The shape of the cross-section directly affects the area moment of inertia of the tow as well as the torsional constant, which both have the potential to affect the bending stiffness of the plate. Finite element models were constructed to investigate the magnitude of these effects on the bending stiffness. No significant difference was observed between models that represented the twisting deformations that were observed and models that did not incorporate this deformation. These results indicate that the bending stiffness has little dependence on the deformation of the tow cross-section. As the shear angle in the plates increased, the thickness of the plates also increased. The change in the thickness of the laminate is directly related to the only partially responsible for the change in the bending stiffness of the plate.

REFERENCES

- [1] S.V. Hoa. Principles of the Manufacturing of Composite Materials. DEStech Publications; 2009.
- [2] M.W. Hyer and S.R. White, *Stress Analysis of Fiber-reinforced Composite Materials*, DEStech Publications, Incorporated, 2009

- [3] A.B. Strong. *Fundamentals of Composites Manufacturing - Materials, Methods, and Applications* (2nd Edition). Society of Manufacturing Engineers (SME); 2008.
- [4] R.M. Jones, *Mechanics of composite materials*, CRC Press, 1998
- [5] P. Brøndsted, H. Lilholt and A. Lystrup, Composite materials for wind power turbine blades, *Annu Rev Mater Res*, **35**, 2005, pp. 505-38
- [6] P.K. Mallick, *Fiber-reinforced composites: materials, manufacturing, and design*, CRC press, 1993
- [7] J. Cao, R. Akkerman, P. Boisse, J. Chen, H. Cheng, E. De Graaf, et al., Characterization of mechanical behavior of woven fabrics: experimental methods and benchmark results, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **39**, 2008, pp. 1037-53
- [8] P. Buckenham, Bias-extension measurements on woven fabrics, *Journal of the Textile Institute*, **88**, 1997, pp. 33-40
- [9] J. Wang, J. Page and R. Paton, Experimental investigation of the draping properties of reinforcement fabrics, *Composites Science and Technology*, **58**, 1998, pp. 229-37
- [10] D. Lussier and J. Chen, Material characterization of woven fabrics for thermoforming of composites, *Journal of Thermoplastic Composite Materials*, **15**, 2002, pp. 497-509
- [11] G. McGuinness and C. ÓBrádaigh, Characterisation of thermoplastic composite melts in rhombus-shear: the picture-frame experiment, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **29**, 1998, pp. 115-32
- [12] A. Prodromou and J. Chen, On the relationship between shear angle and wrinkling of textile composite preforms, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **28**, 1997, pp. 491-503
- [13] O. Rozant, P.-E. Bourban and J.-A. Manson, Drapability of dry textile fabrics for stampable thermoplastic preforms, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **31**, 2000, pp. 1167-77
- [14] U. Mohammed, C. Lekakou, L. Dong and M. Bader, Shear deformation and micromechanics of woven fabrics, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **31**, 2000, pp. 299-308
- [15] P. Badel, E. Vidal-Sallé, E. Maire and P. Boisse, Simulation and tomography analysis of textile composite reinforcement deformation at the mesoscopic scale, *Composites Science and Technology*, **68**, 2008, pp. 2433-40
- [16] M. Barburski, I. Straumit, X. Zhang, M. Wevers and S.V. Lomov, Micro-CT analysis of internal structure of sheared textile composite reinforcement, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **73**, 2015, pp. 45-54 (<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2015.03.008>).
- [17] T. McBride and J. Chen, Unit-cell geometry in plain-weave fabrics during shear deformations, *Composites science and technology*, **57**, 1997, pp. 345-51
- [18] B. Zhu, T. Yu and X. Tao, An experimental study of in-plane large shear deformation of woven fabric composite, *Composites Science and Technology*, **67**, 2007, pp. 252-61
- [19] M. Barburski, S.V. Lomov, F. Lanckmans, F. de Ridder and I. Verpoest, Experimental Study of Steel and Glass Knitted Fabrics Thickness under Pre-Strain and Shear, *Key Engineering Materials*, **554**, 2013, pp. 385-90
- [20] D.S. Ivanov, C. Van Gestel, S.V. Lomov and I. Verpoest, In-Situ Measurements of Fabric Thickness Evolution During Draping, *AIP Conference Proceedings*, **1353**, 2011, pp. 924-9 (doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1063/1.3589634>).
- [21] Twintex(R) Thermoplastic Polypropylene Glass Roving. www.fiberglassindustries.com: Fiber Glass Industries; 2014.
- [22] C.J. Mitchell, K.A. Fetfatsidis, J.L. Gorczyca and J.A. Sherwood, Material Characterization and Discrete Mesoscopic Modeling of Cured Composite Materials, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, submitted for publication, pp.
- E.J. Barbero, *Introduction to composite materials design*, CRC press, 2010